

Subject: Political Science**LYCEUM INDIA****Journal of Social Sciences****Title: Issues of Corruption: Roots and Remedies****Author: Dr. Padma Lochan Barma
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Abstract: Corruption is a pervasive issue that undermines governance, economic growth, and social equity worldwide. It stems from deep-rooted factors such as weak institutional frameworks, lack of transparency, and unchecked power dynamics. This article explores the multifaceted nature of corruption, tracing its origins in political, economic, and cultural contexts. It also highlights the devastating consequences corruption has on public trust and development. Furthermore, the article examines potential remedies, including institutional reforms, enhanced accountability mechanisms, and the promotion of ethical leadership. By addressing both the roots and remedies of corruption, this discussion aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how societies can mitigate its destructive impact.

Keywords: corruption, transparency, governance, accountability, institutional reform

Introduction

In the post-liberalization era the state of India has witnessed numbers of scams and scandals which were never before in its history such as the biggest ever Coalgate scam of Rs.186,000 Crores, 2G Spectrum allocation scandal of Rs176,000 Crores and the scams of Commonwealth Games, Satyam, Telgi, Bofors, Adarsh Housing, Harshad Mehta, Ketan Parekh and the list goes on. This is at the macro level. When we look at the micro level it is horrible as brought out by the staunch Gandhian Anna Hazare where he exposes how the basics of the poor are directly deprived by the local officials being hand in gloves with the contractors and public representatives and other influential by resorting to shameless corruption practices which even deprive them of their square meals of a day. Baba Ramdev reiterates of bringing back black money deposited in foreign accounts to India to be used for rural development. A study reveals that right from Nehruvian era i.e. 1948 to 2008 the illicit flows of funds (IFF) from India to foreign banks have been to the tune of \$213.12 Billion or 17.7% of India's GDP by a complex interplay of structural factors and issues of governance. The Global Financial Integrity Report reveals that between 2002-2011, \$343 billions of black money has been transferred overseas. In 2011 alone, it has earned the notoriety of being the third largest exporter of black money of \$84.93 billion to foreign accounts. When one compiles various reports on black money deposited abroad by the Indians it stands at a staggering \$1,450 billion-more than the national income (The Pioneer,11.01.2014). In this context that the paper makes a humble attempt to define what corruption means (which has become so pervasive) and trace out the root causes of it and tries to put forward possible remedies to this phenomenon. In case at this stage some sort of solution is not brought out by discovering definite governing principles in the prevailing governance system to check the cancerous corruption then it may evaporate the belief that the state continued to exist for the sake of good life of the people- at least the common people (Aam Aadmi). Broadly, on the basis of thoughts of two great political philosophers namely Plato and Mahatma Gandhi the paper tries to incorporate the ideas of both specially the later to the prevailing system of governance if at all practicable.

The Problems

Why prevalence of neck-deep corruption in every spheres of lives in today's governance & deliverance system? What are the root causes? What are the factors contributing so much for its wide spread? What are its remedial measures? What are the ways out? How to tackle these situations? Are there any solutions to these ills? Of course, the pundits say where ever there is problem there is solution.

Before answering above questions, it is pertinent to know what corruption is, what are the areas of corruption and their impact on the society and the state system?

Understanding the Basics

The word “corrupt” means a wide variety of behaviours in an individual’s economic and political settings from illicit or illegitimate behaviour which is considered undesirable by the person holding the office. Scientifically it is used in the backdrop of sociology and politics. It means misuse of an office-government or private- for private interest. The behaviour of those involved in a corrupt practice is either illegal or contradictory to the behavioural rules associated with the office. The violation of office rules occurs purposefully to the advantage of the person holding the office. Benefit may be either in material or immaterial forms directly or indirectly gainful to the person holding the office. Prestige by corrupt practice is an example of immaterial gain & benefit to family members constitutes indirect gain by the misuse of an official position.

According to Cremer there are three areas of misuse by officials which involve in the definition of corruption-

- i) Bribery
- ii) Misappropriation of funds by an office bearer and
- iii) Nepotism.

Bribery

Cremer says it is a trade-off between two shareholders or two groups of shareholders - one who bribes and one who accepts bribe. The one who bribes or active shareholder secures in exchange of money (the bribe) or some kind of good a service that he would otherwise not have received at all. The corrupt service might be the issuance of license or the awarding of a public contract to the one who does the bribing. The one who accepts a bribe is an official or holds a similar position of trust. In guaranteeing a bribe service & in accepting a bribe, an official misuse his position & thus breaches the rules tied to his position. Cremer categorizes services traded for money or for gains with a monetary value into many groups.

Misappropriation

According to Cremer misappropriation can be affected by civil servants who have some scope in deciding how to allocate the state budget. It can occur by the individual deed of an official. Contrary to bribery, this offence does not require a contract with a partner. However, it is more than just a question of deviant individual behaviour on the part of some official. In misappropriation it is essential to falsifying receipts for those who are working in government, developmental aid either in operational or managerial posts. To quote Cremer, “the most important procedures by far in securing misappropriation is the kickback tied to contract awarded by corrupt officials. The party who wins the contracts in agreement with the official involved charges more than the market price or the price that would have been set in a proper bidding procedure; the contractor then passes the extra charge back to the officials who awarded the contract who keeps it for private expenditure. In the field of development aid collusion in procurement process complemented by kickback & bribery is very probably the most significant form of corruption in terms of frequency.”

Nepotism

It can happen when an official abuse his power-position to control access to employment in an official circle. The official responsible for recruitment favours in total disregard of existing rules to the members of his own ethnic group people from his locality or people with the same political affinities. In

broader sense it can occur when an official gives preferential treatment to said people in awarding privileges such as license or contracts.

After discussing the theoretical aspects of corruption in brief, for our better comprehension of the issues of corruption and analysis, it would be better to move to our earlier modest attempt to find out the root causes of corruption and propose lasting & ethical solution basing upon the thoughts of two great political philosophers Plato and Mahatma Gandhi. The paper tries to incorporate the ideas of both specially the later to the prevailing system of governance if at all practicable. Firstly, let's discuss with the Plato's analysis of corruption and then move to Mahatma Gandhi's.

The Roots

To the first two questions, as earlier raised, Plato analysing human nature says, corruption occurs because of greed and luxury culture of the human beings. Since human beings are not satisfied with simple life they are acquisitive, ambitious, competitive and jealous. They are quickly tire of what they have and desire for what they have not. The strange thing is they hardly desire anything unless it belongs to others. The immediate outcome is the encroachment of one person on another, one group upon the territory of another, the rivalry of groups for the rich resources of the nature like mines, lands, water and others. This gives birth to development of trade and finance creating class divisions in the society. Therefore, Plato warns, "any ordinary state is in fact two states, one the city of the poor, the other of the rich, each at war with the other; and in either division there are smaller ones- you would make a great mistake if you treated them as single whole i.e. state as one entity". Elaborating it further Plato says, writes Durant, human behaviour flows from three chief sources. They are desire (synonyms are appetite, impulse, instinct), emotion (spirit, ambition and courage) and knowledge (thought, intellect and reason). The former has its seat in the lions-acquisitive and blind for material quest, the middle in the heart-embodiment of feeling & courage and last in the head which is the eye of desire and can become the pilot of the soul. Their will is a light rather than a fire, whose haven is not power but wisdom and truth. According to Plato these are the persons who stand aside unused by the world. All these are inherent in every human being but differ in degrees.

Plato clarifies in his ideal state that, in the perfect state the industrial forces would produce but they would not rule; the military forces would protect but they would not rule; the forces of knowledge and science & philosophy would be nourished and protected and they would rule. Unguided by knowledge, the people are a multitude without order, like desires in disarray: the people need the guidance of philosophers as desires need the benightment of knowledge. Ruin comes when the trader whose heart is lifted up by wealth, becomes the ruler or when the general uses his army to establish a military dictatorship. The producer is at best in the economic field, the warrior is at his best in battle; they are both at their worst in public office; and at their crude hands politics submerges statesmanship. For statesmanship is a science and an art; one must have lived for it and been long prepared. Only a philosopher-king is fit to guide a nation. Until philosophers are kings, or the kings and princes of this world have the spirit and power of philosophy, and wisdom and political leadership meet in the same man, cities will never cease from ill, nor the human race.

Stiglitz (2002) delineates how the IMF and the WB safeguards the interest of the rich countries. He says the interest of the commercial or financial interest prioritizes only after the interest of the formers. It is intriguing that two world majors- the World Bank & the International Monetary Fund - working in developing countries are headed by either the Europeans or Americans having their appointments in closed door contrary to their experience in those countries.

Digging deeper, further he reveals that representing one's own country does not mean that they represent the interest of the poor. In IMF it is the finance minister and, in the WTO, it is the trade/commerce ministers who represent countries and they are closely connected with particular constituencies/interest in their countries. At the same time both type of ministers represents the interest of the business community who need to see new markets opened up for their products and producers of goods which compete with new imports. Basically, as profit driven they are, they hardly keep any concerns either for consumers or labour or environment issues. Their concerns remain confined to removal of only trade barriers. The decisions of those institutions necessarily reflect the perspective & interest of those who make the decisions. Their policies and programs are interlinked with the financial or commercial interest of the G-7 countries.

The revelation provided by Stiglitz proves that the developing country like India is ruled by traders and business communities or say the corporate worlds and the consequences are disastrous - perverted political system where corruption figures atop. S.P.Shukla an ex-bureaucrat and the member of the Planning Commission of India narrates thus, "from my own experience as a bureaucrat first & later as an activist observer of society and Government I have scan how this process of corruption has evolved. The fundamental reason for the steady increase in corruption in the post-economic liberalization period is that "market has entered government. Corporate houses have started deciding policies & the price of government transactions. They are not only interacting & interfering with individual officer or politician but also with political parties & system as a whole". This seems to be the biggest challenge at the moment to save from the oligarchic rule whose sole motive is only profit with total disregard for ethics, principles and humanism and the whole creation and not in the happiness and welfare of common citizens as propounded by Chanakya.

The Solution

What is the way out? Is there any ethical/ moral or political solution to corruption? Will it ever stop? The questions are very difficult to answer. Only time will tell. Gandhian thought has some answer which prescribes five principles to those who are in public life which can cure ills of mind as traced by Plato in the analysis of human nature, if practiced truthfully. Those are i) truth, ii) non-violence, iii) Brahmacharya or chastity, iv) control of the palate, v) Non-stealing & Non-possession.

Truth: It has been derived from the Sanskrit word 'Sat' which means 'being'. Nothing exists without truth. It does not mean of speaking of Truth only but it should be practiced in thought, in speech and in action. When one realizes in its fullness nothing remains to understand. It is because all knowledge is inherent in it. To quote Gandhiji, "if we once learn how to apply this never-failing test of Truth, we will be able to find out what is worth doing, what is worth seeing, what is worth reading". However, to achieve Truth it involves self-suffering, even unto death. And here there will be no trace of self-interest. There will be no place of cowardice, no place of defeat".

Now question arises how to apply Truth in our day to day life? According to Gandhiji devotion to Truth is the only justification for our existence. Wherever we are or wherever we may be, our day to day activities ought to be cantered on Truth. It ought to be very basis of our life. When this stage is reached other principles of right living will come without effort and obedience to them will be instinctive.

Non-Violence (Ahimsa): Hurting to somebody else undoubtedly a part of ahimsa. But it has a broader meaning. Gandhian rule of ahimsa defines that nobody should be hurt by evil thought, by undue haste, by lying, by hatred, by wishing ill to anybody is ahimsa. This is what happening in our public life every day i.e. to be corrupts at every step of our daily activities. It is infringed when we hold on to what the rest of the

creation needs. Both Ahimsa and Truth are interlinked as without the former it is impossible to seek the latter. According to Gandhi ahimsa is the means and Truth is an end. In case we follow justified means, we will reach our goal sooner or later. It can't be fulfilled without total selflessness. It otherwise implies universal love i.e. to see all human beings as one's kith & kin¹⁸. This is the very vital thing we utterly missing for which we profess corruption and guided by narrow interest. When somebody rises to the height of universal love he/she may not go for evil practice.

Brahmacharya or Chastity: It bears two meaning, one brahma- meaning truth and charya means course of conduct. Thus, bramacharya implies code of conduct to search for Truth. In other words, it refers to control of five senses or control of all the organs of sense. And one has to go for control of all senses. Even a single sense can't be neglected as this would tantamount to violate brahmacharya. In the words of Gandhi, "to hear suggestive stories with the ears, to see suggestive sights with the eyes, to taste stimulating food with tongue, to touch exciting things with the hands, and then at the same time to expect to control the only remaining organ is like putting one's hands in the fire and expecting to escape being burnt". Due to negligence of all these in our life we are hankering after only mundane things compromising hard earned human values to gratify our organ senses. In case this principle is practiced in letter & spirit, corruption of minds can be cured from the root and can make it a thing of the past.

Control of the Palate: It has close connection with the practice of the brahmacharya. Without control over the palate, the latter can't be achieved at all. Food has to be taken as medicine and not as tasty, crunchy and crispy to fill the stomach like garbage. Foods quantities should be limited to the needs of the body just as medicine. Loving and developing an attitude for the pleasant taste will definitely go against the brahmacharya rule. Gandhi says, let such foods be cooked which will help us keep fit for the service of the mankind instead of becoming slaves to our sense organs. This has a clear message that Gandhi wants to pass us that when millions starve for food, riches are dying of over-eating. John Chipman in CBC news writes, "Everyone knows that we eat too much- we are bombarded with warnings about obesity epidemic every day. But all those extra calories are not only a threat to our waistlines; they are threat to global security as well". Like Gandhiji Pope Francis equates food waste with "stealing from the table of the poor and the hungry".

Non-Stealing: Gandhi says, we as human beings consciously or unconsciously are guilty of theft. It is considered theft to part something from another even with due permission if one has no actual need of it. Any single piece of thing should not be received if there is no need. Gandhi explains, we remain unaware of things about our real needs and most of us unjustifiably multiply our wants and unknowingly make thieves of ourselves. Gandhi provides a definite solution for this by adopting a principle of non-stealing by which one can bring down one's wanted to his or her requirement to the proportion. According to Gandhi's firm conviction today's world of poverty is because of the violation of the principle of non-stealing. If this principle followed properly much of the world poverty can be solved. Gandhi even talks of mental theft which is to desire for acquisition of anything belonging to others. Stealing of ideas is also like stealing of valuables. Even the wise have committed such theft in the past. Thus, non-stealing requires one to be humble, thoughtful, vigilant and of simple habits as described by Plato in his ideal state.

Non-Possession: This can be described as self-imposed poverty in Gandhi's term. Other than life's necessities, one should not have more than required things to create scarcity for others. According to Gandhi, possession means stocks for the future which is against a seeker after the Truth. Since Truth happens to be the name of the God, God in no way stores for the future. He does create according to the requirements of the creation. Gandhi explains since we as human being repose faith in Him, we must be assured that He will

bestow on us every day our daily bread. Our ignorance to the above has given birth to inequalities with all the miseries prevailing around us. To quote Gandhiji,” the rich have superfluous store of things which they do not need and which are therefore neglected & wasted; while millions are starves to death for want of sustenance. If each retained possession only of what he needed no one would be in want & all would live in contentment”.

Conclusion

Gandhi’s thought may seem impracticable to treat the ills of mind used in our daily public life but not impossible. When Nelson Mandela, Dalai Lama, Aung-Sang-Su-Ki and now Anna Hazare could spearhead national movements (like India Against Corruption) in their own countries by following the Gandhian path of peace and non-violence and some could win Noble prizes, why not Gandhian values mentioned above can be spread and inculcated in the minds and hearts of our rulers, public servants and among the citizens to bring total reforms right from their entry into the public life. Emergence of Aam Aadmi Party in Delhi’s state assembly election under the stewardship of Arvind Kejriwal in the recent past seems a ray of hope in this regard!

References

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3. 12522I, Chapter-I, Book-I, The Politics, Aristotle, Translated by Ernest Barker, Oxford World Classics.
4. PP-9, Chapter-II, Corruption & Development Aid, by Georg Cremer and Translated by Elizabeth Schuth, Viva Books, 2010.
5. Those categories are – 1) in bribery dealings, the procedures of selection can be influenced to the briber’s favour, 2) in the given dealings the briber pockets the higher profits, 3) the briber quickens the decision or administrative processes to ward off costs, 4) the bribe serves to obtain an illegal contract which has been committed by paying off implementing authorities or law enforcement agencies and 5) the briber prevents threats, obstacles etc imposed on him by officials. It can be vice versa also.
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9. Ibid. PP-22,
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11. Chapter-IV, Globalization & its Discontent, 2000. PP-18,
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13. Frontline, Dec 04-17, 2010, Vol-27, No.25, PP-6.
14. Verse 1.19.34, in Kautilya’s Artha Shastra.
15. Yervada Mandir, Vol-IV, The Selected Works of Gandhiji, Navjeevan Press, Ahmedabad. PP-211,
- 16., Ibid. PP-214
17. Ibid. PP-215
18. Ibid. PP- 218
19. According to FAO, 1.3 billion tons of food or about 1/3 of all the foods produced globally was lost or wasted annually. In developed societies the average person wasteful about 100 kg of food every year. The World Food Program estimates that 870 million people worldwide do not have access to enough food to be healthy.

20. Institute of Applied Manpower Research, affiliated to the Planning Commission of India paints a grim scenario on country's poverty front in its recent report- released by its Vice-President Montek Singh Ahlualia . It mentioned that despite the economy growing at 6% on an average; it has not helped reduce poverty in the country. Despite affirmative action by the Government high incidence of poverty persists among the SCs,STs and Muslims.The figure of poverty during 1973-74 was 332 million which remained constant even in 1983-84 and reduced slightly to 320 million during 1993-94 and 2004-05 status shows poverty at stagnant. Income gap between the rich and the poor has widened with top 5% of the HHs possessing 38% of the total assets and the bottom 60% HHs owning a mere 13%.
- 21.Vol-IV, The Selected Works of Mahatma Gandhi,Navjeevan Press, Ahemdabad, PP-222.

